

AI-POWERED YOLOV11 FRAMEWORK FOR AUTOMATED DETECTION OF COMMON EYE DISEASES WITH HIGH DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY

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Abstract

Eyes are a precious gift of God and play a vital role in the human body. The natural beauty of the world can be seen with the help of the eyes. Indulging in any disease of the eyes can create problems with seeing properly. There are many diseases of the eye, but **cataract, conjunctivitis, pterygium, and stye** are the common eye diseases that cause vision loss and blindness. Traditional methods of eye treatments are painful and sometimes may cause blindness. Many studies have been conducted to cure these diseases, but have not yielded satisfactory results. In this study, we proposed a Deep learning model, YOLOV11, which enhances diagnostic precision accurately and speedily. This is a reliable and cost-effective automatic system in the medical field for eye disease detection analysis. The overall accuracy of this system is 87.62%.

INTRODUCTION

Eyes are an incredible gift from God. With the help of our eyes, we can see the unbelievable world around us [1]. Eyes help to learn about our surroundings. Eyes help to see safely whether we are driving or walking [2]. Without sight, life would be much tougher and bound. Eyes are important in daily life. With the help of our eyes, we can read books, learn new things, and do our jobs. Cooking, pressing the clothes, washing the clothes, and cleaning the house would be tough without sight [3]. Eyes help to watch movies, play games, or admire art. Eyes are vital for all the activities we do. Eyes can help to understand their emotions and feelings of other people without saying a word [4].

Eyes protect us from fast-moving cars coming at us [5]. Eyes should be kept aware of surroundings, which is important for safety.

Absence of sight can be very tough, and often leads to isolation and sadness. That's why care of the eyes with regular check-ups is vital. Keep this precious gift safe as long as possible so that we can see the beauty of the world around us. There are numerous eye diseases, but **cataract, conjunctivitis, pterygium, and stye** are the common diseases that can cause vision loss and blindness [6] [4] [7].

Figure 1: Common Eye Diseases

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 2.5 billion people have vision problems [8]. These common eye diseases are distinct eye conditions. These can affect different parts of the eyes. In **Conjunctivitis**, the white part of the eyes (Sclera) becomes red due to inflammation of the conjunctiva. It can also cause burning of the eyes, irritation in the eyes, or gritty feelings in the eyes. It can cause blindness and vision loss if we do not treat it timely but it can be treated in time. In **Stye** disease, the eyelid area becomes red due to the inflammation of the eyelash follicle. Eyes might become watery due

to irritation. It does not directly affect on eyes' vision. It can cause problems, putting pressure on the eyeball, and can temporarily become the reason for slight bulging. **Pterygium** can cause redness, burning, and irritation. Its effects on the cornea. Large growth on the cornea can cause blurred vision. **Cataract**, the Eyes become sensitive due to light, which can produce discomfort. The main causes include difficulty in seeing in the dark, blurred vision, and faded colors. It's a primary cause of vision loss if not treated properly on time.

Figure 2: Eyes affected by Cataract and Pterygium disease

Figure 3: Eyes affected by Conjunctivitis and Stye disease

The appropriate treatment of the eyes can prevent the loss of vision. Many Traditional and Non-traditional treatment methods are being used for the treatment of eyes [9] [10]. Traditional treatment methods are very painful, and sometimes may cause blindness due to the negligence of the Doctors. Sometimes, Traditional treatment methods may be expensive due to the long period of treatment process. Non-traditional treatment methods may involve innovative technologies. Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the field of health has brought perfect innovation [11]. Now, eye diseases can be easily treated without loss of vision because there is no chance of Doctor negligence. Many studies have been conducted on the treatment of eye diseases by using AI. Deep learning, a subfield of Machine learning of sub field AI started work. Deep learning popularity begins with the success of the convolutional neural network (CNN), **Lecun et al.** In image ImageNet competition, krizhevsku used a DL model [12]. After that, Alex-Net on ImageNet, InspectionV3 [13], Google-Net [14], Dense-Net [15], VGG-Net [16], and Res-Net [17] were developed with successful results. An improved deep learning model, U-Net, achieved 95.6 % accuracy in detecting blood vessels [18]. A dual-channel asymmetric CNN based on U-Net achieved 96.3 % accuracy [19]. Similarly, another study (filtering and multilevel morphological operations) achieved 96%

accuracy and 75% sensitivity [20]. Mask R-CNN + Dense-Net models were used on glaucoma and achieved 96% accuracy [21]. [Masum Shah Junayed](#) et al. introduced the RestNet-18 model, achieving 98.9% [22]. Syeda Nabila Shirazi et al. introduced the Cataract-Net model results, achieving a highest 99.13% accuracy [23]. Although these models give accurate and high-precision values, but are not good for real-time object detection.

Study Gap in previous literature:

Traditional Methods are lengthy, expensive, and painful procedures. Sometimes due to human errors can lead to blindness. AI-based models like U-Net, Mask-RNN, Dense-Net, and Cataract-Net lose their accuracy in emergencies. Many Deep learning models require preprocessed data. They have to face a generalization issue because they were trained on specific datasets and may fail to generalize due to domain shift. They required high computational resources, which are very expensive and difficult. They are trained and tested on limited data and may not reflect the diversity of real clinical cases.

In this study, the proposed model not only focuses only **one or two classes** of eye disease, but it will focus on five eye classes, such as Normal, cataract, conjunctivitis, pterygium, and stye.

Figure 4: Eye Disease classes used in datasets

The Proposed Deep learning model is not only best for real-time object detection but also detects objects speedily and accurately, giving higher precision in a very short time as compared to all other models of either Deep learning or Machine Learning. In Machine Learning models, features are extracted first, then classification is done [24], but in Deep learning models such as YOLO models [25] extract features are extracted and classification is done only in one shot in a very short time. YoloV8 and YOLOV10 models have achieved 83.05 % validation accuracy [26]. The proposed approach (Yolov11 Model) can help us in a short time with more accurate analysis by automating the detection of eye disease classifications such as Normal, cataract, conjunctivitis, pterygium, and stye, which may eradicate the vision loss in people.

Objective of the Proposed Model:

To address the limitations mentioned above, the following objectives are involved in our study:

1. To make a system that will be capable of detecting multiple conditions within one unified framework.
2. Building a system that may increase the efficiency and decrease the latency of the model by real-time object detection performance.
3. To make a system that will perform feature extraction and classifications in a single pass by increasing the efficiency to prevent eye vision loss through automated analysis support.

Methodology:

The diagram presents a structure and methodology for the detection and classification of eye disease using a Deep learning model, Yolov11.

Figure 5: Proposed Model

The system has two main phases: the first phase involves the data collection and model training, and the second is the operational phase for real-time object detection. In the first phase, data of images containing different conditions like normal, cataract, stye, conjunctivitis, and pterygium are collected. Then these raw images go into a pre-processing step to increase the quality of the images. After applying augmentation, we get the refined data, that data is fed to the proposed model for training the proposed model. During the training phase model learns the pattern and features of images. If the model makes the wrong predictions, it uses the internal parameters to minimize the errors through a process called back propagation. Back propagation helps the model to learn better over time. After training, the model becomes so smart that it can detect any condition of eye disease. Before the deployment of the model in the real world, we test and check it by giving it many unseen images. The performance evaluation of the model is calculated by performance metrics such as Precision, Recall, F-1 Score, and Accuracy. If the dataset is imbalanced, we usually calculate the F-1 score. In real use, when we feed the new eye image to the model, the images go through the same steps as involved in the training of models. The model processes the images and gives the results based on previously learn data in the training phase. These

results will be helpful for the Doctor to quickly detect the disease using AI.

Dataset Collection:

A dataset (Namely **Se-Mongta**) consisting of 16668 images, enclosing labeled images for five eye disorders (Normal, Cataract, Conjunctivitis, Pterygium, and stye) was downloaded from **Robo-flow**, a platform that delivers annotated image datasets. Auto-orientation, resizing, and augmentation are already applied in the dataset. Images enter the preprocessing step. Data augmentation controls the size, robustness, rotation, flipping, zooming, and brightness changes in images. Single Image Review is designated for confirming preprocessing results before batch processing the entire dataset. Preprocessing and augmentation are done for balancing the classes, better learning patterns, and to decrease the unpredictability of the dataset. The refined dataset is entered into the Deep learning model YOLOv11.

Data Splitting:

The proposed model is trained by a refined dataset of images so that it can learn specific features of the disease of each category. 13728 (82%) images are used for training, 1962 (12%) images for validation, and 978 (6%) images for testing the model.

Figure 6: Data Splitting Chart

Data distribution:

The data distribution chart explains the no. of images and consistently labeled instances for five eye conditions: Cataract, Conjunctivitis, Normal, Pterygium, and Stye. Cataract is the most signified class with 734 images and 734 instances, presenting perfect stability. Other classes like Normal, Pterygium,

and Stye also appear to have a near one-to-one ratio between images and instances. Minor dissimilarities exist in Conjunctivitis and Pterygium, where some images comprise multiple lesions. Overall, the dataset is comparatively balanced and well-structured, making it suitable for training machine learning models for eye disease detection.

Figure 7: Data Distribution Graph

Training the Yolov11 Model:

The proposed model is trained on Google Colab, an open-source platform. Internet connectivity is needed for training the model. It is easy and efficient because all the libraries can be installed easily. It provides a GPU environment for some period of time, which can increase the training speed of the model. In this study, we trained the model with 100 epochs to achieve the best performance.

The process of building and testing the entire pipeline of the methodology. It provides information about the model that how well the model will work on unseen data to detect the classification.

Performance Evaluation:

The performance of models is measured by performance metrics such as Precision, Recall, F-1 Score, Confusion metric, and Accuracy.

Simulation:

Table 1: Performance Metrics

Metric	Formula
Confusion Matrix	Table containing outcomes such as T_p , F_p , F_n , T_n
Accuracy	$(T_p + T_n) / (T_p + T_n + F_p + F_n)$
Precision	$T_p / (T_p + F_p)$
Recall	$T_p / (T_p + F_n)$
F-1 Score	$2 \times (\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})$

The performance evaluation of the model in all classes reveals valuable perceptions. For Cataract, the model's performance is good. The model represents strong accuracy with a recall, precision, and F-1 score of 92.38%, 95.65% and 93.98% respectively. Conjunctivitis represents an even better result with a

high precision of 98.42%. Normal eye class has a relatively high precision of 85.89%. Pterygium class achieves an outstanding precision of 96.77. Styte shows decent performance, achieving a precision of 91.59%. The results are fairly strong; there is an improvement in recall for this category.

Figure 8: Class-wise performance metric Evaluation

Confusion Matrix:

A **confusion matrix** is a performance measurement tool for classification models. It equates the predicted

class with the actual class and displays where the model was correct or incorrect for each class.

Table 2: Confusion Matrix

Predicted \ Actual	Cataract	Conjunctivitis	Normal	Pterygium	Styte
Cataract	703	1	1	1	0
Conjunctivitis	1	309	1	1	0
Normal	0	1	341	0	1
Pterygium	0	0	0	420	0
Styte	0	0	0	0	305

Accuracy Curve: A plot that shows how a model's accuracy changes with time over different conditions. It is used in ML to visualize performance.

Figure 9: Accuracy Graph

Precision Curve: It shows how the precision values change over training epochs. Thresholds.

Figure 10: Precision Confidence Curve

The model reveals **robust classification ability** for eye diseases, especially for normal and conjunctivitis conditions. The combined class curve attainment has a precision of **1.00 at 0.956 confidence**, reflecting a **well-calibrated and highly accurate system**,

appropriate for clinical deployment in automated eye disease diagnosis.

Recall Curve: It tells about the under-fitting and over-fitting of the models.

Figure 11: Recall Confidence Curve

The model attains **excellent recall at low confidence thresholds**, meaning it can detect most cases when it is less strict. Conversely, as confidence increases, recall declines, particularly for **Cataract and Pterygium**, which proposes a trade-off between model inevitability and its ability to detect diseases. Overall, the model continues to have a **balanced recall**, with **Normal and Conjunctivitis** being the most consistently detected.

F-1 Score Curve:

It balances both **precision** and **recall**, especially vital in cases of **imbalanced datasets**. Because the accuracy may mislead the performance of the model. In an imbalanced dataset, the condition F-1 Score is considered as accuracy.

Figure 12: F-1 Confidence Curve

The model demonstrates **excellent classification performance** for **conjunctivitis** and **normal eye** conditions. The optimal balance between confidence and accuracy is attained around a **confidence**

threshold of 0.34, making it a commendable setting for clinical or real-time diagnostic use.

Model Output:

Figure 13: Model Predicted Output

Performance Evaluation of Trained Model:

Figure 14: Performance of the trained model graph

Conclusion:

Eye diseases like cataract, conjunctivitis, pterygium, and stye are the cause of vision loss worldwide. Traditional methods require more time, are expensive, and prone to human error. Although

Machine Learning and Deep learning models such as U-Net, Dense-Net, and Cataract-Net achieve high accuracy, they lack real-time object detection capability. In this study, a novel deep learning-based object detection model, Yolov11, is proposed for

real-time object detection of five distinct conditions. Yolov11 leads the Machine Learning and other deep learning models by offering feature extraction and classification in just one shot in a very small time with high speed. The model builds upon the success of prior Yolo architectures, giving high validation accuracy, precision, and speed. The proposed model determines strong potential for deployment in automated analysis systems, especially in infrastructure resources. Its high ability to detect multiple eye conditions accurately makes it a valuable tool for the early diagnosis and prevention of sight loss.

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